

A FOURTH WAY: CULTURAL HERITAGE AS THE KEY TO UNLOCKING SUSTAINABLE PLACE-DRIVEN INNOVATION

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Abstract: Set against a powerful context of political instability and global economic uncertainty, and driven in part as a response to unprecedented challenges including Brexit and UK regional devolution, the paradigm of ‘place’ has seen rapid incorporation into national and global policy making and practice. Interpretation, development and evaluation of place has thus far been dominated by two fairly static definitions: a physical understanding of ‘a place’ as a defined, geographic territory and a socio-economic understanding of place as a self-contained economic and social system. This paper introduces cultural heritage as a third and critical criterion in realising a more comprehensive understanding of place. Through pragmatic application of mixed methods including ethnographic interview, questionnaire and survey, design science and action research, and utilising cutting-edge ‘living platform’ mapping techniques in analysis and visualisation, the research seeks to interrogate the inter-relationship between place and innovation, exploring that nexus through a cultural heritage lens. Through integrating critical factors of space and time, it creates a new conceptual framework for sustainable place-driven development and presents a new ‘place-driven’ economic paradigm, within which a whole series of previously accepted tripartite models can be elevated; presented collectively as ‘a fourth way’.

Keywords: Culture, Heritage, Innovation, Place, Sustainability.

1. INTRODUCTION/BACKGROUND

The paradigm of ‘place’ has seen rapid incorporation into policy making and practice, in the UK and across the world. The speed at which its incorporation has occurred has arguably, and in some cases demonstrably, led to the concept’s application while not being fully formed. To some extent as a result of this, and an associated need for anchoring it as a concept, its interpretation, development and evaluation has thus far relied on and been dominated by two fairly static definitions: a physical understanding of ‘a place’ as a defined, geographic territory and a socio-economic understanding of place as a self-contained economic and social system.

These well-practiced tenets fit ‘place’ comfortably within the current and predominantly capital-driven economic paradigm, in which the spatial/territorial understanding of place fits neatly with the notion of capital ‘spatial fix’ (Harvey, 2001) and the socio-economic application of ‘place’ mimics the defined parameters of a capital labour market.

Less comfortable is the interaction between these static definitions of ‘place’ and the inherently dynamic innovation landscape. The construct of ‘embeddedness’ is critical to this nexus (as, for example, applied to the Smart Specialisation innovation process, which requires ‘an accent on fostering regional embeddedness’ (Ketels, 2013b)), and its application in this sense tends to refer to a deep immersion in one or more acknowledged industrial, geographic or economic strengths of a particular place; characterised as ‘place-based’ innovation.

This paper introduces cultural heritage as a critical criterion in realising a more comprehensive understanding of place, and in effect as a key driver in catalysing a less constrained and more fluid and reciprocal interaction between place and innovation.

2. LITERATURE

2.1 The innovation-place nexus: Smart Specialisation

Smart Specialisation is a central concept in the ESRC's vision for Europe's innovative future (EC 2016). It is based on the principle of defined economic systems (predominantly regions) generating new specialisms through a process of discovery which builds on unique local assets and competences, toward economic growth. Smart Specialisation Strategies (S3) (Foray 2015) translate the academic concept of Smart Specialisation into policy, allowing regions to prioritise concentration of resources as the basis for competitive advantage. S3 is based on five core design principles: entrepreneurial discovery, mid-level (predominantly regional) granularity, inclusiveness, an expectation of progress (specifically in that priorities will not be supported forever) and the promotion of experimentation and risk. S3 is now firmly established as a key feature in European innovation policy. Since 2013, it has been a compulsory ex-ante conditionality requirement for EU member states and regions accessing EU funds to have an S3 in place (EC 2013a).

The rapid rise of S3 from academic theory to legal requirement has mirrored its own design principles. It is an experimental strategy which has made extraordinarily fast-paced and dynamic progress, benefiting from and contributing to a focus on entrepreneurialism, innovation and inclusion, and the growing movement toward regional, devolved and 'place-based' development. Whilst there is clear ideological synergy between the regional focus of S3 and the place-based approach, "Smart Specialisation Strategies... were initially developed from an a-spatial concept (and) have needed to be reworked and redefined in the context of regional analysis" (EC 2013b: 12). The EC's 2013 report on S3 and cluster policy, based on the findings of a special advisory group chaired by Ketels (EC 2013b) advocates for regionally distinct, place-based approaches to S3, as opposed to "place-blind interventions", setting out a desired logic for S3 delivery which prioritises regional context, participation and ownership and place-specific future visioning. The report identifies a lack of stakeholder engagement, insufficient analysis of regional assets and a "Tendency for regional strategies to chase the same "bandwagon" sectors" (EC 2013b:11) as key S3 policy flaws.

Place is implicit in the level of granularity required by S3. The co-relation between place and innovation, via S3, is made explicit by the 2009 Barca report (and has been recently restated by McCann, 2015). The Barca report defines a place-based approach as "a long term strategy aimed at tackling persistent underutilization of potential and reducing persistent social exclusion in specific places through external interventions and multi-level governance" (2009:3). Whilst this is a useful definition, and of its time, both S3 and place-based concepts have since continued to evolve, and whilst the concept of 'place' remains "incompletely developed" (Taylor & Devaney 2014: 6), in emerging just ahead of the place-based paradigm, S3 has been able to respond to and absorb a deepening understanding of what 'place' means.

2.2 Place-based innovation

A portfolio of work from The Brookings Institute's Bass Initiative has been seminal in framing emerging thinking around the interconnectivity between innovation and place. Katz and Wagner (2014) assert a typology based around three models of 'innovation districts' in cities: the 'anchor-plus' model, in which a clustering of assets and infrastructure occurs around the presence of an anchor institution, such as a university; the 're-imagined urban areas model', in which former industrial or warehousing sites undergo large-scale regeneration (often, Katz and Wagner observe, to be found in historic waterfront districts); and the 'urbanized science park' model, which sees new industry and commercial activity in suburban or ex-urban areas growing around clustered scientific activity.

In a later review of this predominantly spatial analysis of innovation strategy, Katz, Vey and Wagner (2015) introduce "the imperative to combine and activate physical assets in ways that create vibrant "places", quoting Ethan Kent, Chief Executive of The Project for Public Spaces' description of place as "environments in which people have invested meaning over time. A place has its own history—a unique cultural and social identity that is defined by the way it is used and the people who use it." (Katz, Vey and Wagner, 2015: 3).

2.3 Place-based innovation and cultural heritage

Place-based innovation, and S3, tends to focus on the acknowledged strengths of a place. Often, these strengths are so acknowledged because they have a basis in a place's industrial or cultural heritage. Greater Manchester (GM), for example, is pioneering innovative models of advanced manufacture in its work with Graphene, building on its recognised historic strength in manufacturing.

As with the dominant understandings of 'place', heritage too tends to be characterised as a fixed and static concept, based primarily on the 1972 UNESCO World Heritage Convention definition of cultural heritage as 'monuments, groups of monuments and sites'. The ICOMOS Nara Document in 1994, which called for cultural context in regards to permanence, recognising, for example, the cultural heritage value - but impermanence - of ritually rebuilt wooden temples and mud huts, pioneered a school of thought which has since introduced a more fluid understanding, particularly in regard to cultural heritage, and which was underscored by the formal recognition of 'intangible heritage' by UNESCO in 2003. This thinking continues to influence contemporary cultural heritage research, such as the Royal Society of Arts' advocacy for 'Networked Heritage' and 'Heritage Citizens' in its 'Heritage, Identity and Place' portfolio of work, co-sponsored by the Heritage Lottery Fund (RSA, 2016) While there is a wealth of emergent academic literature on cultural heritage and place, the relationship between cultural heritage and innovation is a relatively fresh domain. From a policy perspective, where a relationship is noted, the focus tends to be on the economic value of cultural heritage, principally through tourism. The report of the EC Horizon 2020 expert group on cultural heritage (EC 2015) asserts that "modest investment in cultural heritage can pay substantial dividends" and that the EU should "vigorously promote the innovative use of cultural heritage for economic growth." (EC 2015:8).

2.4 Embeddedness

Ketels, as previously noted, calls for ‘an accent on fostering regional embeddedness’ (Ketels, 2013b) in his 2013 review of European S3 and cluster policy. The call is made in mitigation of a number of noted policy flaws, principally the tendency for regions to choose ‘bandwagon’ sectors, such as digital and bioscience, as S3 specialisms. It marks a pivotal point in the development of S3, and in the developing ‘place’ paradigm, as both move from superficial ‘place-based’ strategies to strategies ‘embedded’ and demonstrably grounded in place.

There is some tension between this call for ‘embeddedness’ and the short-term risk taking and learning, regenerative shedding and re-definition of priorities which is actively encouraged in the process of Smart Specialisation (Foray, 2015). This regenerative process in support of innovation has a long and rich provenance, dating from Schumpeter’s “gale of creative destruction”, the “process of industrial mutation that incessantly revolutionizes the economic structure from within” (1994: 82) and its rise to prominence in the 1950s. More recently, Schumpeter’s influence can be seen in Harvey’s ‘spatial fix’ (2001), Castells’ ‘space of flows’ (2010), and in the explicit incorporation of ‘creative destruction’ as a key driver in Smart Specialisation itself (Foray 2015).

A better fit can arguably be found in the sociological, neo-substantivist paradigm around ‘embeddedness’ brought forward by Granoveter (1985), the central tenet of which is based on the theory of individual economic agency being “embedded in concrete, ongoing systems of social relations” (Granoveter, 1985). This delicate balance between a static, ‘concrete’ embeddedness and dynamic, ongoing systemic change resonates well with the required relationship between place and innovation. Application of this more fluid and culturally aware definition of ‘embeddedness’ as a key construct in both the place and innovation paradigms challenges the place/innovation nexus to respond.

3. METHODOLOGY

The research has employed a hybrid methodology of design science and action research, augmented through literature review, questionnaire, interview and case study.

3.1 The design science model

The methodology has drawn primarily on the design science model, which incorporates six sequential stages (explicate problem, define requirements, design and develop artefact, demonstration, evaluation and communication of knowledge), and which focusses on the development of an artefact. Action research methods have been integrated into this overarching design science framework in support of the demonstration and evaluation stages.

The sequential nature of design science approach offers a flexibility and adaptability that is supremely necessary in a project of this nature, which is not only focussed on fast-changing concepts such as place and innovation, but which is current and as such susceptible to political, economic and external influences. Already, the research has been required to adapt in the face of Brexit and subsequent potential changes to European policy (and in particular to the UK’s S3 policy), in addition to other unforeseen circumstances affecting the selected case studies, including a hurricane and a political protest. The approach adopted has not only

supported the research in meeting these challenges, but has also allowed for the research to respond to emerging thinking in the field. Adopting a dual focus on the artefact and the context has also been helpful maintaining a balance, and in ensuring neither aspect overly dominates the research; the two aspects in fact reciprocally ‘feed off each other’, ensuring freshness and relevance.

For the purposes of the research, ‘the artefact’ in question is a novel method for articulating and evaluating innovation strategies, incorporating cultural heritage as a critical criterion. ‘The requirements’, the contextual conditions for the artefact, focus on ‘place’ and are represented by the emerging hierarchal place taxonomy.

The first stage of the research (relating to stage one of the design science methodology, ‘Explication of the problem’) saw findings from the literature review synthesised to create a core research framework. That framework was tested and refined through a pilot case study focussed on Greater Manchester (GM)’s S3 strategy, incorporating a series of scoping interviews with key GM public sector, private sector and academic stakeholders.

3.2 ‘The artefact’ – the ‘Sustainable S3 Wheel’

Based on preliminary findings from the literature review and scoping stage, an initial sketch of a novel evaluation tool for innovation strategies (‘the artefact’) was conceived. The sketch visualised an inherently complex concept through a user-friendly metaphor, the “Sustainable S3 Wheel”, in which the wheel is representative of an innovation economy, structurally supported by three axes of ‘place’, two of which represent the traditional concepts of spatial and social considerations, and introducing a third axis to represent cultural factors (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: The “Sustainable S3 Wheel” (sketch)

3.3 ‘The requirements’ – case studies in ‘place’

A series of case studies was selected to further test and refine the structure of the artefact, and to generate an initial understanding of the requirements, that is, the contextual role of ‘place’. Case study selection drew on the work of Katz and Wagner (2014), focussing in the US on Boston (Kendall Square) and Seattle (South Lake Union), and in the UK on Manchester’s Oxford Road Corridor as examples, respectively, of the ‘anchor plus’, ‘re-imagined urban

areas’ and ‘urbanized science park’ models of innovation district. Case studies were conducted through a mix of quantitative and qualitative methods supported primarily by four analytical tools: survey, questionnaire, interview and presentation of the case study results themselves.

A second phase of case studies, looking in more depth at Manchester’s Oxford Road Corridor and including other selected ‘innovation districts’ across GM such as The Sharp Project, The Federation and Salford’s Media City UK is in progress to allow development, testing and application of an emerging ‘place hierarchy’ taxonomy and of the nascent evaluation tool (based on spatial, social and cultural criteria), enabling critical assessment of these areas as ‘innovation districts’ in relation to the findings from the earlier case studies.

3.4 Action Research – M4

The development, demonstration and evaluation stages of the research have been augmented by adoption of action research methods, principally centring on an ambitious practical project which has responded to emerging findings to establish ‘M4’, a civic innovation space designed to represent the emerging ‘fourth typology’ of innovation district. Launched in May 2017, M4 operates as a network, and while not confined to a geographic space, its administrative base is located in The Federation in central Manchester, which also houses a number of tech and social enterprises. The M4 project will incorporate an in-motion evaluation of the effects of its introduction on the GM innovation ecosystem over a twelve-month period.

3.5 The ‘Living Platform’

A cutting-edge data visualisation technique, the ‘Living Platform’, developed by the University of Salford’s ThinkLab and School of the Built Environment (SoBE) and launched in June 2017 is being utilised to collate and demonstrate the results of the second phase of case study, enabling evaluation of the spatial, social and cultural aspects of the selected innovation district to be cross-referenced, analysed and presented via a real-time, dynamic platform, and allowing for spatial and temporal factors, emerging as critical to the research, to be factored into results. A still showing ‘innovation hotspots’ displayed on the platform from the in-progress case study focussing on MediaCityUK in Salford, Greater Manchester, is shown as Figure 2.

Figure 2: Still from *The Living Platform* showing ‘innovation hotspots’ at MediaCityUK

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 The ‘Sustainable Innovation Wheel’

“The Sustainable Innovation Wheel”, a prototype tool for the evaluation of innovation economies (piloted in its initial stages with a focus on S3 strategies) has been developed as both an output and tool for the research (see Figure 3).

Figure 3: *The Sustainable Innovation Wheel*

In this novel evaluation model, each axis represents a critical quality in successful innovation economies. The first axis – the *where* – represents spatial factors, incorporating granularity, proximity and built environment considerations; the second axis – the *who* – represents social factors, incorporating inclusivity, participation and stakeholder engagement, and the third axis, completing the spokes in the wheel, represents cultural factors – the *what* – those aspects of place such as heritage, identity and culture, that make a place distinctive and its S3 specialisms unique. The fourth aspect, the catalyst to make the wheel spin is the *how*.

Too often, the perception – and reality – of innovation sees an overly-dominant focus only on the strengths of a particular place. This tends to come at the expense of the application of innovation capacity in addressing place-based weaknesses, social demands or issues of need. Successful and sustainable innovation has the opportunity to bring a vast range of different actors together in addressing a whole range of collective place-based goals. Instead, the

dynamic nature of the “Sustainable Innovation Wheel” allows for and predicts an innovation economy which not only responds to, but feeds off, all aspects of a place, and the entire spectrum of place-related indicators; a ‘place-driven’ innovation economy (see Figure 4)

Figure 4: A ‘place-driven’ innovation economy

4.2 An emerging ‘place’ hierarchy

Exploring the conceptual relationships between the *where*, *what*, *who* and *how* of the “Sustainable S3 Wheel”, and considering their individual and collective application to both the ideological development of S3 and the nature of the three established (Katz and Wagner, 2014) innovation districts allows us to assert and observe an emerging hierarchy of ‘place’, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: An emerging ‘place’ hierarchy

INNOVATION DISTRICT	DRIVER	CONSTRUCT	CONCEPT	PLACE
Urbanized Science Park	Private	Spatial	Where	Place-blind
Regenerated Urban Areas	Social/ 3rd	Social	Who	Place-based
Anchor Hub	Public/Academic	Cultural	What	Place-grounded
Citizen-led	People	Civic	How	Place-driven

The introduction of a cultural construct unlocks a dynamism in the innate characteristics of place-related innovation, which in turn asserts a fourth type of quasi-spatial innovation district; the civic space; an assertion which introduces ‘people’ as catalytic agents at the nexus of place and innovation, and – conceiving of the movement between concepts along a vertical axis - introduces ‘time’ as a key consideration in understanding how all of those dynamic dependencies interact.

4.3 Culture and place-grounded innovation

Evidence from both the Boston and Seattle case studies demonstrates the dominance of large, private companies in the selected areas of those cities (Kendall Square and South Lake Union, respectively), identified in the Katz and Wagner piece (2014) as exemplars of ‘innovation districts’. Both districts are physically located at some distance to the urban core (and in Boston’s case separated by a river), and show limited resonance with each city’s distinctive cultural heritage, which is demonstrably better integrated into more organic innovation offers emerging in ‘downtown’ areas such as Pioneer Square, in Seattle, and the Seaport District, in Boston, both of which are driven by a nascent small enterprise scene. Greater Manchester’s ‘Oxford Road Corridor’, representing the ‘urbanized science park’ typology also demonstrates a marked literal and figurative distance from Manchester’s city centre.

Key stakeholders in both US cities have, however, acknowledged the importance of cultural activity to innovation, with one civic leader in Boston commenting that “Innovation happens when culture and the economy clash together”. In support of this assertion, the Boston Mayor’s Office is currently supporting a programme of micro-grants through its *Boston Creates* initiative specifically for artists and creatives working in the innovation space, described by Interviewee A as “watering the innovation seedlings”.

Cultural appropriation is evident in a number of case studies in the second phase of the research, including for example, The Sharp Project and its strong heritage links to the Sharp processing plant, an industrial brand synonymous with Manchester and the former occupier of its site (the site layout forms The Sharp Project logo), and at The Federation, where local street artists Nomad Clan have recently been commissioned to create art on the walls of the central collaborative workspace, shown in Figure 5. The art depicts ‘worker bees’ (symbolic of Manchester) and incorporates various cultural references including Manchester United and City football strips, Coronation Street characters and famous Mancunian musicians. The artwork also includes quotes from Tony Walsh’s poem (writing under the pen-name of Longfella) ‘This is the Place’, which came to particular prominence as an anthem for the city following the terrorist attack at Manchester Arena in May 2017.

4.4 Place-driven innovation in practice

Evidence from the Boston and Seattle case studies demonstrates how both cities are beginning to apply their acknowledged innovation strengths to tackling their key urban and social challenges. In Boston, widely acknowledged as a global leader in innovation thanks largely to the presence of Harvard University and MIT and the clustering effect of large corporate tech and biotech firms around those anchor points, there is a growing sense of the need to better connect its anchor institutions and citizens, and to apply the city’s vast knowledge capital to its ‘wicked problems’. Positioned on the Atlantic coast, and with much of its development along that coastline built on landfill, climate change and rising water levels are of particular concern. 2016 saw the inaugural Hub Week, a ‘festival of innovation’ which included a series of open-sourced, place-based challenges inviting innovative responses to issues around the city’s bodies of water, generating a range of actionable and multiple-bottom line ideas, including water cleansing bio-pellets made from the city’s significant food waste.

In Seattle's Pioneer Square district, fast-emerging as a grassroots innovation 'hotspot', Impact Hub Seattle acts as a centre-point for the district's social enterprise, digital and creative businesses. It is currently hosting a collaborative work programme to focus the district's collective innovation capacity on the city's homelessness crisis, declared as a 'state of emergency' by the city's Mayor in 2016. Steve Johnson, CEO of Impact Hub Seattle describes the hub's role in the programme as "a catalytic convenor between the place and the people". The importance of people as citizens in Seattle's emerging 'place-driven' innovation ecosystem was noted by several civic leaders, with one describing "the role of government" as "empowering people on the ground so that those solutions that citizens already have, which have been lying dormant, can be brought to life".

Findings from both the pilot case study in GM (January 2016), and the second phase of case study research, in-progress, suggest that while a number of social enterprises and initiatives exist with a focus on the city-region's social challenges, there is a distinct lack of understanding of this activity as being in the innovation space, alongside a continued ideological and fiscal investment focus on the Oxford Road Corridor. There is little too in terms of infrastructure and networks designed to enable GM's citizens to participate in this innovation space. The M4 project, launched in May 2017, has been designed as a citizen-led civic innovation space with the stated mission of filling these gaps. It is an ambitious piece of action research, and includes an in-motion evaluation of its introduction to the GM innovation ecosystem, which will report in September 2018.

5. CONCLUSIONS

5.1 Place, innovation and embeddedness

There is a clear tension between the static (spatial and socio-economic) definitions of 'place' and the inherent dynamism of innovation. At the heart of this tension is a problematic spatiotemporal relationship, which sees the defined characteristics and spatial territory of place juxtaposed against the fluidity and incompleteness of the innovation process. To date, this tension been alleviated – and arguably avoided – by employing only a very superficial understanding of place in innovation spaces. Urbanized science parks, the first typology of innovation district identified by Katz and Wagner (2014), and still stereotypical 'go to' in the concept of places for innovation, have historically shown little resonance with place and have maintained a cultural and geographical distance.

Ketels' call for 'regional embeddedness' (Ketels, 2013b) in Smart Specialisation strategies, a principal driver in European innovation policy, brought this tension into sharp focus, and marks a pivotal point in both the innovation and place paradigms, and where they intersect. The concept of embeddedness had existed implicitly in the 'place-based' strategic space, but its explicit introduction via this intervention, particularly as a response to regions selecting 'bandwagon' specialisms (pointing to the superficiality of the 'place-based' approach), came as a challenge to the innovation landscape to incorporate and demonstrate a deeper understanding of place.

This 'cultural awakening' of the innovation space has coincided with a developing understanding of cultural institutions as 'anchor hubs', as markers and stewards of a place and its heritage, alongside the predominantly academic institutions traditionally identified as 'Anchor Hubs' (as in the 2014 Katz and Wagner piece). This in turn has led to an 'opening up' of those, historically isolated, academic institutions, and their pro-actively seeking out

more progressive and active roles in local communities (Jackson & McInroy, 2016). As academic institutions continue to better integrate with place, so too we can see a move away from innovation as the acknowledged domain of universities, through culture, and toward the civic space.

5.2 Cultural heritage and place-driven innovation

Evidence from the case studies suggests we are at a particular ‘point in time’ in the integration of cultural aspects in the place/innovation nexus. That point sits between the ‘place-grounded’ and ‘place-driven’ concepts presented in Table 1. There is evidence in some case studies of place-driven activity, specifically innovation in response to a broader place spectrum (incorporating weaknesses as well as strengths), and also evidence of a growing acknowledgement of the potential role for citizens – people – as innovators.

Cultural *heritage* is key at and for this ‘point in time’ juncture. The dual effect of heritage, recently defined by the RSA (2015) as “anything inherited from the past that helps us, collectively or individually, to understand the present, and create a better future” is both to underscore the temporal nature of that juncture in relation to the innovation/time axis, and, through its inter-relationship with ‘identity’ to introduce people into the space/place equation. That said, there remains a current fixation on districts and spaces ‘for innovation’, buildings and places in which innovation happens, and in some instances, a sense of overcompensation through cultural re-appropriation. The general direction evidenced across the case studies, however, is toward this more fluid and responsive ‘place-driven’ innovation model. By reversing the concept from the (conceptually insular) constraints of ‘place-based’ to the (conceptually open) movement of ‘place-driven’, the initial spatiotemporal tension is effectively eliminated.

5.3 Place-driven innovation and sustainability

Elimination of this conflict would in itself suggest that the ‘place-driven’ model is more sustainable than previous approaches. At a basic level, the model contributes to the sustainability of place through the inclusion of people as catalysts, an inarguably renewable resource, and by its advocacy for innovation to address needs and challenges.

There is a more complex relationship between the model and sustainability in terms of permanence. Clearly, the model calls for openness, fluidity and dynamism, and advocates for responsiveness to people and place over time as key to sustainability. It is not, however, a rejection of permanence, or prioritising one over the other. Conceptually speaking, the “Sustainable Innovation Wheel” requires all ‘fixed’, ‘permanent’ elements – including the *where*, the *who* and the *what* (spatial, social and cultural), to be in place and balanced in order to turn; it cannot turn on the *how* alone.

5.4 A Fourth Way

Taken cumulatively, the evidence asserts a ‘place-driven’ fourth typology of innovation district; a citizen-led, people-driven, civic innovation space. This quasi-spatial district is non-territorial, eschewing to some extent the notion of ‘districts’ and ‘hubs’, in favour of an open and dynamic interconnected network. By transcending the territorial boundaries of place, it avoids the ‘unintended impacts’ of hyper-investment in specific geographic districts, promoting instead a new and democratised approach to innovation, at the heart of an inclusive, and people-driven economy. Over the next twelve months, the ‘M4’ action research programme will seek to test the viability and validity of the fourth innovation space in practice, using a series of human-centred value metrics related to the four constructs (spatial, social, cultural and civic). This is an innovation economy, liberated. A fourth way.

6. REFERENCES

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